

Historical museums of China

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Abstract: This article covers the history of China's historical museums and the history of their origin, many years of Customs and traditions. Most of the exhibits are high-quality items collected by Chinese emperors. The National Palace Museum began its history with the Palace Museum in the closed city of Beijing, whose large-scale works of art and artifacts were built on the imperial collections of the Min and Sin dynasties.

Key words: China, palace, museum, samat, exhibit, arteftk, nation, history, ancient, material, management, central, library, treasure, communication, monument, cultural heritage.

The National Palace Museum, located in Taipei, Taiwan, has a permanent collection of about 700,000 Chinese artifacts and artworks, making it one of the largest museums in the world. The exhibits reflect China's 8,000-year history from the Neolithic to the present. Most of the exhibits are high-quality items collected by Chinese emperors. The National Palace Museum began its history with the Palace Museum in the closed city of Beijing, whose large-scale works of art and artifacts were built on the imperial collections of the Min and Sin dynasties. The National Palace Museum was originally established on 10 October 1925 by Feng Yusyan, The Last Emperor of China, military commander, as a Palace Museum in a closed city. The museum's artifacts consisted of valuables from the former imperial family.

In 1931, shortly after the Mukden Incident, The Nationalist government of Generalissimo Chan Kay - Shi ordered preparations to evacuate the museum out of town in order to prevent the museum's valuables from falling into the hands of the Japanese Imperial Army. As a result, from February 6 to May 15, 1933, the Palace Museum's Department of precious antiquities, consisting of 13,491 boxes and 6,066 boxes, the Summer Palace and the Imperial Hanlin Academy were moved to Shanghai, divided into five groups. In 1936, after the construction of a warehouse in the Chaotian Palace in the Taoist monastery, the collection was moved to Nanjing. As the Imperial

Japanese army entered a major conflict during World War II deeper into the country during the Second Sino-Japanese War, the formation was moved through three routes to several areas, including Anshun and Leshan, until the surrender of Japan in 1945. In 1947, she was placed in a depot in Nanjing. The collection of the Beijing National Palace Museum, Nanjing Museum preparatory department, Nanjing library and National Library of China was stored in a railway depot in Yangmei after being moved through the Taiwan Strait and later moved to a cane sugar mill warehouse near Taichung. In 1949, the administrative government created the National Beijing Palace Museum, the preparatory Office of the National Central Museum, and the Joint Management Office for the National Central Library to oversee the creation of the museum. For security reasons, the United Management Office chose the mountain village of Beigou, located in Wufeng, Taichung, as the new storage location for the collection. The following year, the collection held at the cane sugar mill was moved to a new location in Beigou.

With the restoration of the National Central Library in 1955, the collection of the National Library of Beijing was simultaneously moved to the National Central Library. The Joint Management Office of the Beijing National Palace Museum and the preparatory Office of the National Central Museum stood in Beigou for another ten years. The office received a grant from the Asia Foundation to build a small exhibition hall in the spring of 1956. The exhibition hall, which opened in March 1957, was divided into four galleries that could display over 200 exhibits. In the fall of 1960, the office received a \$ 32 million Taiwan grant from the United States Agency for International Development. The Government of the Republic of China (ROC) has donated over \$ 30 million to establish a special fund for the construction of a museum in Waishuansi, a suburb of Taipei. Construction of the museum in weishuansy was completed in August 1965. The new museum site received the name "Chung-Shan Museum" in honor of Sun Yat-Sen, the founder of XR, and was first opened to the public on the occasion of the 100th anniversary of Sun Yat-Sen's birth. Since then, the Museum in Taipei has been displaying the collections of the National Palace Museum of China and the preparatory Office of the National Central Museum. In the 1960s and 1970s, the National Palace Museum was used by Gomindan to support his claim that the Republic of China was the only legitimate government of all of China. Because it remained the sole custodian of traditional Chinese culture in the context of social change and cultural change.

The Government of the people's Republic of China (PRC) has long stated that the collection was stolen and that it is legally owned by China, but Taiwan rates its collection as a necessary effort to protect it from destruction, especially during the Cultural Revolution. However, in recent years, ties with this treasure have warmed, and the Palace Museum in Beijing has agreed to give the National Palace Museum monuments for exhibitions since 2009, according to the head of the Palace Museum Zheng Sinmiao, the exhibits in the museums of China and Taiwan are "the cultural heritage of China, which people along the Taiwan Strait jointly own". A number of excavated artifacts dating back to the Tan dynasty and Son dynasties, some of them attributed to Emperor Zhenzzung, fall into the hands of the gomindan General Ma Hongy, who later refused to publish the finds. Artifacts included a white marble tablet from the Tan dynasty, gold nails, and metal bands. It was not until General Ma's death in 1971 that his wife traveled from America to Taiwan to hand over the treasure to Chan Kay Shi, who turned over the artifacts to the National Palace Museum. The National Silk Museum of China in Hangzhou hosts the convention “colorful Asia: an exhibition of Asian costumes” dedicated to the 19th Asian Games. 20 museum exhibits of Uzbekistan will also be displayed in it, “he said Gazeta.uz” to the press service of the foundation for the development of Culture and art. The National Silk Museum of China is located next to the West Lake in Hangzhou, which is included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. The exhibition space of the museum is about 1200 square meters. This museum ranks 9th among 6,000 museums in China. The exhibition presents about 150 dresses from different regions of Asia. Several craftsmen are also invited, who are successors to the ancient style of printing, weaving and embroidery.

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